

Soil & crop management

Applied rice research program in northeast Brazil

Kenneth C. Ellis, Consortium for International Development, Cochabamba, Bolivia, and L. D. Haws, International Rice Research Institute

Local rice varieties and cultural practices were compared with new varieties and methods under rainfed upland conditions during the 1974 rainy season at three locations in Maranhao and Piaui states, northeastern Brazil. Each plot was 100 sq m (10 m × 10 m); we harvested 64 sq m (8 m × 8 m) for yield data.

At two locations, the rice seed was broadcast; at one location, it was planted in rows. Herbicides (Machete and Stam F-34) were used to control weeds. No insecticides were used except at one location where infestation of ear head bugs was severe.

Results (see table) indicated that:

- 1) the broadcast method of seeding rainfed upland rice was highly successful;
- 2) herbicides gave excellent weed control and were cheaper than hand weeding;

3) the semidwarf varieties IR8 and CICA-4 yielded significantly more than local varieties grown under similar

conditions; 4) the use of fertilizers on the tall local variety Dourado Agulha was not profitable.

Cost of major inputs, and returns per hectare for rainfed upland rice in Maranhao and Piaui states, Brazil.

	Costs and returns (\$/ha) for					
	Seed	Fertilizers	Pesticides	Total inputs	Gross income	Net return
	<i>At Piripiri</i>					
IR8	9.33	139.00	36.00	185.00	877.00	692.00
CICA-4	9.33	86.00	36.00	131.00	585.00	454.00
D. Agulha	9.33	86.00	36.00	131.00	328.00	197.00
D. Agulha	9.33	00.00	36.00	45.00	328.00	283.00
	<i>At Teresina</i>					
IR8	14.00	56.00	36.00	106.00	889.00	783.00
CICA-4	14.00	38.00	36.00	87.00	561.00	474.00
D. Agulha	14.00	38.00	36.00	87.00	202.00	115.00
D. Agulha	14.00	00.00	36.00	50.00	203.00	153.00
	<i>At Santa Ines</i>					
IR8	14.00	56.00	25.00	95.00	636.00	541.00
CICA-4	14.00	38.00	25.00	77.00	546.00	469.00
Sagrimao	14.00	38.00	25.00	77.00	416.00	339.00
Sagrimao	14.00	00.00	25.00	39.00	220.00	181.00

Analysis of yield components in ricefields in the Punjab, India

S. S. Saini and G. S. Brar, Punjab Agricultural University Regional Rice Research Station, Kapurthala, Punjab, India

The production of food grains in the Punjab - one of the smaller states of India - more than trebled from 1965 to 1975. During this period, rice production increased about five times (from 292,000 to 1,445,000 tons) and yields increased from 1.0 to 2.6 t/ha. The increases were mostly due to the rapid spread of the high-yielding varieties IR8 and Jaya. The varieties now cover more than 90 percent of the rice area. Although these rices can yield more than 10 t/ha under Punjab conditions, average yield is stabilized at 4 t/ha.

Table 1. Analysis of yield components and yield in 47 rice fields in the Punjab during kharif 1975.

Character	Optimum value to obtain 100 quintal per hectare	Values from survey of 47 fields			
		Mean value	Range	Samples with optimum or higher value	
				(no.)	(%)
Hills (no./sq m)	33	22	12 - 41	4	8.5
Ear-bearing tillers (no./sq m)	363	139	70 - 280	-	-
Ear-bearing tillers (no./hill)	11	6.3	2.9- 11.8	1	2.1
Non-ear bearing tillers (no./sq m)	-	13	3 - 40	-	-
Nonear bearing tillers (%)	-	9.3	2.9- 36.4	-	-
Grains/panicle (no.)	103	110	77 - 214	21	44.7
Fully ripened grains (%)	85	82.19	57.2- 96.8	22	46.8
1,000-grain wt (g)	30	28.1	24.0- 32.0	16	34.2
Grain weight (g/sq m)	1000	507.3	220 - 986	-	-
Grain yield (ql/ha)	100	50.73	22.0- 98.6	-	-